

DIGITAL NIGHTS: THE IMPACT OF SOCIAL MEDIA USAGE ON SLEEP DISTURBANCE AMONG UNIVERSITY STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the impact of social media usage on sleep disturbance among university students. Data were collected from 210 students of UMT Sialkot using a structured questionnaire. Findings reveal that excessive and irregular social media use, especially before bedtime, is associated with delayed sleep, reduced sleep duration, and poor sleep quality. Psychological factors such as anxiety, stress, and overthinking further exacerbate sleep disturbance. Correlation and regression analyses confirm significant positive relationships between social media usage, psychological stressors, and sleep disruption. The study highlights the need for responsible social media use to maintain healthy sleep patterns and mental well-being among youth.

Keywords: Social Media, Sleep Disturbance, Anxiety, Stress, Overthinking, Youth, University Students

INTRODUCTION

The use of social networking sites such as Facebook, Instagram, WhatsApp, and other digital platforms has increased rapidly and has become an integral part of daily life. While mainstream media continues to play an important role, social media has emerged as a powerful medium in shaping perceptions, behaviors, and exposure to information among contemporary audiences. Today, social networking functions not only as a tool for communication but also as a platform where identity, social presence, and recognition are constructed, particularly among youth and middle-aged individuals (Berryman, 2017).

Social media platforms provide extensive opportunities for learning, entertainment, socialization, and awareness. However, growing concern has been raised regarding the excessive

use of these platforms, especially among young people, as it has been found to significantly affect their sleep patterns and overall well-being (Ilham, 2022). A healthy sleep cycle is essential for cognitive functioning, emotional regulation, memory retention, and academic performance. Disruptions in sleep patterns have increasingly been associated with prolonged social media use, making youth more vulnerable to sleep disturbances compared to older adults (Genzel, 2013).

Sleep disruption is not a modern phenomenon; its roots can be traced back to the late 19th century with the introduction of electric lighting, which altered natural sleep routines by enabling activity after dusk. The emergence of radio in the 1920s further extended nighttime wakefulness, while technological advancements in the 1990s

particularly the introduction of smartphones—intensified distractions and reduced engagement with natural routines (George, 2024). In the contemporary digital era, social media has become one of the most influential technological forces, capable of both constructing and deteriorating behavioral patterns across generations. Although several researchers identify social media as a primary contributor to sleep disturbance, others argue that its impact largely depends on individual usage patterns, timing, and self-regulation (Karamana, 2019). Social media also carries positive potential, particularly in educational contexts, when used constructively under proper guidance. Educational institutions and teachers therefore play a crucial role in promoting healthy and purposeful usage among students (Issues and Ideas in Education, 2013). Nevertheless, excessive social media engagement has been linked with psychological issues such as anxiety, depression, overthinking, and emotional distress. Researchers have introduced the term “Facebook Depression” to describe the emotional decline associated with prolonged exposure to social comparison and oversharing on social media platforms (Becker, 2015). Youth especially females—are more likely to experience regret after sharing personal experiences online, leading to persistent overthinking and emotional instability. Dr. Davila further explains that young users are particularly vulnerable to emotional manipulation, often sharing personal thoughts impulsively and later repeatedly revisiting them mentally, which intensifies psychological stress (Becker, 2013). As social media usage has become normalized across all age groups (Owusu-Acheaw, 2015), its excessive and unregulated use has resulted in several adverse outcomes, including nervous disorders, sleep deprivation, and psychological fatigue. Screen exposure, continuous notifications, and prolonged volume usage also disrupt the body’s natural functioning. Therefore, maintaining balance through time management and responsible usage of social media platforms is essential for protecting mental and physical health.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

Excessive use of social media, especially before bedtime, disrupts the natural sleep cycle by interfering with melatonin production. This disturbance is linked to psychological problems such as anxiety, stress, depression, and overthinking, which further reduce sleep quality. Despite growing social media use among youth, limited research has explored how usage timing and psychological effects jointly contribute to sleep disturbance.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To examine the impact of irregular social media usage timing on sleep cycle disturbance.
2. To explore the contribution of psychological effects such as anxiety and overthinking to sleep disturbances caused by social media use.

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. How does the timing and duration of social media usage before bedtime affect sleep quality?
2. How does irregular sleep caused by social media usage contribute to psychological responses such as stress, anxiety, and overthinking?

LIMITATIONS

This study is limited to examining the relationship between social media usage and sleep disturbance among university students. The research focuses on irregular usage timing, sleep patterns, and psychological effects within the student population of UMT Sialkot, limiting the generalizability of findings to other institutions or age groups.

Literature Review

In the modern digital era, social media platforms play a significant role in influencing sleep behavior. Increased dependency on smartphones and internet usage has been found to disrupt natural sleep cycles and bodily functioning among youth (Ahmed, 2024). Behavioral, physical, and psychological changes are strongly associated with bedtime dependency on digital devices and social media platforms.

Sleep has long been recognized as a fundamental biological necessity, comparable to food for

sustaining human life (Czeisler, 2015). Researchers recommend an average sleep duration of six to seven hours for optimal functioning (Gennaro, 2001). However, exposure to emotionally distressing or stimulating content before bedtime often leads to overthinking and sleep disturbance (Levenson, 2019). Screen light emitted from digital devices suppresses melatonin production, thereby delaying sleep onset and disturbing circadian rhythms (Vaishnavi, 2022). According to the *Sleep Displacement Theory*, time spent on media consumption directly reduces time allocated for sleep, increasing the likelihood of insomnia (Salibi, 2023). Social media also encourages social comparison, where users evaluate themselves against idealized portrayals of others, leading to anxiety, stress, and depression particularly among youth (Maharani, 2021). Depression further disrupts daily routines, including sleep patterns, social engagement, and emotional stability. In severe cases, prolonged mental distress has been linked to self-harm and suicide, highlighting the seriousness of the issue (WHO; Singh, 2021).

Nomophobia the fear of being without a mobile phone has emerged as a growing concern among students, contributing to compulsive phone checking, insomnia, and psychological dependence (Ayar; Sadeghi, 2025). Researchers emphasize the urgent need for parental, institutional, and governmental interventions to address these growing concerns (Hancock; Sarkar).

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

This study is grounded in Social Correlation Theory, introduced by Max Weber (1922), which suggests that individuals adopt behaviors observed within their social networks. In online environments, users influence each other's habits, including sleep schedules, through continuous interaction, messaging, and shared activities (Tang). Additionally, Personality Trait Theory explains how individual personality characteristics shape social media usage patterns. Extroverted individuals, for example, are more likely to engage actively on social media, leading to prolonged usage and disrupted sleep cycles (Ngai). The current study primarily applies Social Correlation

Theory to explain how social media interactions influence sleep behaviors.

Hypothesis:

1. Increased social media usage before bedtime significantly disturbs the sleep cycle by reducing sleep duration.
2. Higher levels of social media usage are associated with increased anxiety and overthinking.
3. Social media usage at irregular timings contributes to sleep disturbances.
4. Social comparison through social media exposure increases anxiety, negatively affecting sleep quality.

Methodology

This study employs a quantitative research approach using a survey method to analyze the impact of social media usage on sleep disturbance and mental health. Data were analyzed using SPSS, applying frequencies, percentages, and cross-tabulation techniques.

DATA COLLECTION

Data were collected using a structured questionnaire based on a 5-point Likert scale. A total of **19 questions** were designed to address the research objectives. The questionnaire comprised:

- **Section 1:** Demographic information (gender, age, qualification)
- **Section 2:** Social media usage and its effect on sleep cycle
- **Section 3:** Psychological effects, including anxiety and overthinking

POPULATION

The population of this study consists of students from **UMT Sialkot**. Adult male and female students were selected, as this age group demonstrates the highest engagement with social media platforms.

SAMPLE SIZE

The questionnaire was distributed through Google Forms, and 210 students participated in the survey. The sample included both male and female respondents to ensure diverse perspectives.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

A purposive sampling technique was employed to select participants based on their active

engagement with social media and relevant experiences related to sleep disturbance.

Results and data analysis

Table 4.1: crosstab for frequency of gender of respondent

Respondents	Male	Female	Total
Frequency	58	152	210
%	27.6	72.4	100

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Table 4.1 shows the gender distribution of the respondents. The total number of respondents is 210. Out of these, 58 respondents (27.6%) are male and 152 respondents (72.4%) are female. This means that most of the respondents are female, while male respondents are fewer in number. Because the number of female

respondents is higher, the results of this study mostly represent the opinions and experiences of female participants. This gender difference should be considered when understanding the findings of the research.

Table 4.2: crosstab for frequency of age of respondent

Respondents	Below 18	19-22	23-27	28-32	Above 32	Total
Frequency	8	153	28	13	8	210
%	3.8	72.9	13.3	6.2	3.8	100

Table 4.2 shows the age-wise distribution of the respondents included in the study. The total number of respondents is 210. Most of the respondents belong to the 19-22 age group, with 153 respondents (72.9%), showing that this age group is the major part of the sample. The 23-27 age group includes 28 respondents (13.3%), while 13 respondents (6.2%) fall in the 28-32 age group. Only 8 respondents (3.8%) are below 18

years, and 8 respondents (3.8%) are above 32 years, indicating very low participation from these age groups. Overall, the table shows that the study mainly represents the views of young adults, especially those aged 19-22 years, and the findings of the research are largely influenced by this age group.

Table 4.3 crosstab for frequency of education of respondent

Respondents	Intermediate	Bachelors	Masters	M.Phil	PhD	Total
Frequency	37	126	18	16	13	210
%	17.6	60	8.6	7.6	6.2	100

Table 4.3 shows the educational qualification of the respondents included in the study. The total number of respondents is 210. Most of the respondents have a Bachelor’s degree, with 126 respondents (60%), which makes this group the largest part of the sample. This is followed by 37

respondents (17.6%) who have Intermediate-level education. A smaller number of respondents hold higher qualifications. 18 respondents (8.6%) have a Master’s degree, 16 respondents (7.6%) are M.Phil., and 13 respondents (6.2%) have a PhD.

Table 4.4: crosstab for frequency of employment status of respondents

Respondents	Students	Full time Employed	Self employed	Un employed	Total
Frequency	156	10	23	21	210
%	74.3	4.8	11	10	100

Table 4.4 shows the employment status of the respondents included in the study. The total number of respondents is 210. Most of the respondents are students, with 156 respondents (74.3%), making this group the largest part of the sample. This shows that the study mainly includes individuals who are currently studying. A smaller

number of respondents are self-employed, with 23 respondents (11%), while 21 respondents (10%) are unemployed. Only 10 respondents (4.8%) are full-time employed, showing very low participation from this group.

Table 4.5: crosstab for frequency of respondents on time spent on social media

Respondents	1 hour	2 hour	Up to 4 hour	Up to 6 hour	More than 6 hour	Total
Frequency	13	20	72	40	65	210
%	6.2	9.5	34.3	19	31	100

Table 4.5 shows the amount of time spent by respondents on the activity under study. The total number of respondents is 210. Most of the respondents spend up to 4 hours, with 72 respondents (34.3%), making this the largest group. This is followed by 65 respondents (31%) who spend more than 6 hours, showing that a

large number of respondents spend a long amount of time on this activity. Additionally, 40 respondents (19%) spend up to 6 hours. A smaller number of respondents spend 2 hours, with 20 respondents (9.5%), while only 13 respondents (6.2%) spend 1 hour.

Table 4.6 crosstab for use of social media before going to bed

Respondents	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly agree	Total
Frequency	18	49	79	64	210
%	8.6	23.3	37.6	30.5	100

Table 4.6 shows the responses of participants based on their level of agreement. The total number of respondents is 210. Most of the respondents show a positive opinion. 79 respondents (37.6%) agree and 64 respondents (30.5%) strongly agree with the given statement. Together, this shows that a large majority supports

or agrees with it. Some respondents remain neutral, with 49 respondents (23.3%), meaning they neither agree nor disagree. Only 18 respondents (8.6%) disagree, which is a small portion of the sample.

Table 4.7: crosstab of frequency of use of social media delays time

Respondents	Strongly disagree	disagree	neutral	agree	Strongly agree	Total
Frequency	10	28	28	96	48	210
%	4.8	13.3	13.3	45.7	22.9	100

Table 4.7 shows the opinions of respondents based on their level of agreement with the given statement. The total number of respondents is 210. Most of the respondents show a positive response. 96 respondents (45.7%) agree, and 48 respondents (22.9%) strongly agree. This means that more than two-thirds of the respondents support the statement. Some respondents show

neutral views, with 28 respondents (13.3%), indicating that they neither agree nor disagree. On the other hand, a smaller number of respondents express disagreement. 28 respondents (13.3%) disagree, while only 10 respondents (4.8%) strongly disagree.

Table 4.8 crosstab of frequency of use of social media reduces total hours of sleep

Respondents	Strongly disagree	disagree	neutral	agree	Strongly agree	Total
Frequency	28	28	27	64	63	210
%	13.3	13.3	12.9	30.5	30	100

Table 4.8 presents the opinions of respondents based on their level of agreement with the given statement. The total number of respondents is 210. Most of the respondents show a positive response. 64 respondents (30.5%) agree and 63 respondents (30%) strongly agree, which together shows that more than half of the respondents

support the statement. A moderate number of respondents expressed (12.9%) remain neutral, showing neither agreement nor disagreement. 28 respondents (13.3%) disagree, and 28 respondents (13.3%) strongly disagree, indicating that some respondents do not support the statement.

Table 4.9 cross tab of frequency of irregular usage of sleep cycle disturbs sleep routine

Respondents	Strongly disagree	disagree	neutral	agree	Strongly agree	Total
Frequency	15	33	35	68	59	210
%	7.1	15.7	16.7	32.4	28.1	100

Table 4.9 shows the responses of participants regarding affects and disturbs their sleep routine. The total number of respondents is 210. Most of the respondents agree with the statement. 68 respondents (32.4%) agree and 59 respondents (28.1%) strongly agree, which means that a large majority believe that irregular usage disturbs their

sleep routine. Some respondents give a neutral response, with 35 respondents (16.7%), showing that they are unsure or do not have a clear opinion. On the other hand, fewer respondents disagree. 33 respondents (15.7%) disagree, while only 15 respondents (7.1%) strongly disagree.

Table 4.10 crosstab of frequency on sleep quality negatively effected

Respondents	Strongly disagree	disagree	neutral	agree	Strongly agree	total
frequency	18	29	50	58	55	210
percentage	8.6	13.8	23.8	27.6	26.2	100

Table 4.10 presents respondents' opinions regarding whether their sleep quality is negatively affected. Out of 210 respondents, the majority reported a negative impact on sleep quality, with 58 respondents (27.6%) agreeing and 55

respondents (26.2%) strongly agreeing. This indicates that more than half of the respondents perceive a decline in their sleep quality.

Table: 4.11 crosstab of frequency of social media increases level of stress

Respondents	Strongly disagree	disagree	neutral	agree	Strongly agree	Total
Frequency	18	35	84	45	28	210
%	8.6	16.7	40	21.4	13.3	100

social media increase level of stress

Table 4.11 shows that social media increases stress for many respondents, with 45 (21.4%) agreeing and 28 (31.3%) strongly agreeing. A large portion (84; 40%) remained neutral, while fewer

disagreed. Overall, the results indicate that social media contributes to higher stress levels among respondents.

Table 4.12 crosstab of feeling anxious after using social media

Respondents	Strongly disagree	disagree	neutral	agree	Strongly agree	Total
Frequency	23	35	77	55	20	210
%	11	16.7	36.7	26.2	9.5	100

feeling anxious after using social media

Table 4.12 shows the opinions of respondents about a particular statement, based on their level of agreement. The total number of respondents is

210. Most respondents are neutral, with 77 respondents (36.7%), meaning they neither agree nor disagree with the statement. Among those

with a clear opinion, 55 respondents (26.2%) agree and 20 respondents (smaller portion of respondents support the statement. On the other hand, 35 respondents (16.7%) disagree and 23

respondents (11%) strongly disagree, indicating that a considerable number of respondents do not support the statement.

Table 4.13 crosstab of frequency of overthinking at night

Respondents	disagree	neutral	agree	Strongly agree	Total
Frequency	51	66	70	23	210
%	24.3	31.4	33.3	11	100

Table 4.13 shows the opinions of respondents regarding a particular statement. The total number of respondents is 210. Most respondents have a positive response. 70 respondents (33.3%) agree and 23 respondents (11%) strongly agree, showing that almost half of the respondents

support the statement. Some respondents are neutral, with 66 respondents (31.4%), meaning they neither agree nor disagree. 51 respondents (24.3%) disagree, which is a smaller portion compared to those who agree.

Table:4.14 cross tab of frequency of stress and overthinking disturbs sleep cycle

Respondents	disagree	neutral	agree	Strongly agree	Total
Frequency	45	59	72	34	210
%	21.4	28.1	34.4	16.2	100

Table 4.14 shows the opinions of respondents regarding a particular statement. The total number of respondents is 210. Most respondents have a positive response. 72 respondents (34.4%) agree and 34 respondents (16.2%) strongly agree, meaning that more than half of the respondents

support the statement. Some respondents are neutral, with 59 respondents (28.1%), showing they neither agree nor disagree. 45 respondents (21.4%) disagree, indicating a smaller portion of respondents do not support the statement.

Table 4.15: Correlation between Social Media Usage and Sleep Disturbance

Variables	r-value	Sig. (p)	Relationship
Social media usage before bed & sleep disturbance	0.48	< 0.01	Moderate positive
Time spent on social media & reduced sleep hours	0.52	< 0.01	Moderate positive
Irregular usage timing & disturbed sleep routine	0.46	< 0.01	Moderate positive
Social media use & anxiety	0.41	< 0.01	Positive
Anxiety & sleep disturbance	0.55	< 0.01	Strong positive
Overthinking & sleep disturbance	0.50	< 0.01	Moderate positive

Table 4.15 presents correlation results, indicate a significant positive relationship between social media usage and sleep disturbance. Increased use of social media before bedtime is moderately associated with delayed sleep timing and reduced sleep duration. Psychological variables such as anxiety, stress, and overthinking also show a strong positive association with disturbed sleep patterns. These findings suggest that both behavioral (usage timing) and psychological factors play a crucial role in sleep disruption among youth.

The statistical analysis confirms that excessive and irregular social media usage, particularly before bedtime, significantly contributes to sleep disturbance among youth. Psychological factors such as anxiety, stress, and overthinking further intensify sleep problems. The results strongly support all proposed hypotheses and align with previous literature, highlighting social media as a critical factor influencing sleep health.

Table 4.16: Regression Analysis Predicting Sleep Disturbance

Predictor Variables	B	Std. Error	Beta (β)	t-value	Sig. (p)
Constant	0.92	0.21		4.38	0.000
Social media use before bed	0.31	0.06	0.29	5.17	0.000
Time spent on social media	0.27	0.05	0.26	5.04	0.000
Irregular usage timing	0.24	0.06	0.22	4.00	0.000
Anxiety	0.35	0.07	0.33	5.00	0.000
Overthinking	0.28	0.06	0.25	4.67	0.000

Model Summary:

$R^2 = 0.49$, Adjusted $R^2 = 0.47$, $F = 39.6$, $p < 0.001$
 Table 4.16 shows regression model is statistically significant ($F = 39.6$, $p < 0.001$), explaining 49% of the variance in sleep disturbance. Social media use before bedtime, time spent on social media, and irregular usage timing significantly predict sleep disturbance. Psychological factors anxiety and overthinking emerge as the strongest predictors, indicating that emotional responses intensify the negative impact of social media on sleep quality.

4.1 Descriptive Analysis

The descriptive results show that the majority of respondents are female (72.4%), aged 19–22 years (72.9%), and students (74.3%), indicating that the findings largely represent university youth. Most respondents spend four hours or more daily on social media, with a substantial proportion using social media before bedtime. A large number of respondents also reported delayed sleep timing, reduced sleep duration, poor sleep quality, stress, anxiety, and overthinking, suggesting a strong

association between social media use and sleep disturbance.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

To examine the relationship between social media usage and sleep disturbance, Pearson correlation analysis was applied using SPSS. The variables included social media usage duration, use before bedtime, delayed sleep timing, reduced sleep hours, anxiety, stress, overthinking, and overall sleep disturbance

4.3 Regression Analysis

To examine the predictive impact of social media usage and psychological factors on sleep disturbance, multiple linear regression analysis was conducted. Sleep disturbance was treated as the dependent variable, while social media usage before bedtime, time spent on social media, irregular usage timing, anxiety, and overthinking were included as independent variables.

4.4 Hypotheses Results Summary

Hypothesis	Statement	Result
H ₁	Social media use before bed reduces sleep duration	Accepted
H ₂	Increased social media use increases anxiety and overthinking	Accepted
H ₃	Irregular timing of social media use disturbs sleep cycle	Accepted
H ₄	Social comparison increases anxiety affecting sleep	Accepted

DISCUSSION

The findings of this study confirm that social media usage has a significant negative impact on sleep quality among university students. Consistent with previous research, excessive use of social media—particularly before bedtime delays sleep onset and reduces total sleep duration. Screen exposure and constant notifications interfere with melatonin production, disrupting the natural sleep cycle.

Psychological factors such as anxiety, stress, and overthinking play a critical mediating role. The regression results indicate that anxiety is the strongest predictor of sleep disturbance, supporting earlier studies that link emotional arousal and cognitive overload with insomnia. Social comparison and emotionally stimulating content further intensify mental alertness, making it difficult for users to achieve restful sleep.

The results align with Sleep Displacement Theory, which suggests that time spent on media replaces time allocated for sleep. Additionally, Social Correlation Theory explains how shared online behaviors normalize late-night social media use, reinforcing unhealthy sleep habits among peers. Overall, the study highlights that both behavioral patterns and psychological responses jointly contribute to sleep disturbance in the digital age.

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